

ANGLE DIVERSITY RECEPTION FOR LOS DIGITAL MICROWAVE RADIO

R. W. Hubbard

U.S. Department of Commerce
National Telecommunications and Information Administration
Institute for Telecommunication Sciences
Boulder, CO 80303

ABSTRACT

Digital transmission over line-of-sight (LOS) microwave links is impaired at times by multipath fading in the propagation channel. The multipath can be a result of surface reflections, or induced by atmospheric anomalies such as strong ducting gradients. One principal method of overcoming the effects of multipath is to use a form of diversity transmission and reception. The common forms of diversity in LOS links are frequency and space, or combinations of both in severe cases. This paper describes an alternative form of diversity using angle (of arrival) diversity at the receiving terminal. This form of diversity has the advantages of a) limiting the antenna elevations required for space diversity, and b) spectral efficiency when compared with frequency diversity.

INTRODUCTION

Multipath fading in LOS microwave links has emerged as the predominant factor affecting the performance of digital transmission systems. This fact has become evident from a series of performance tests and other experimental evidence reported in the literature since about 1977. As examples of this literature, we cite the refs. [1] through [7]. One of the first methods available to counteract the degraded performance in an unprotected channel is to use a diversity configuration of the radio system. The most common forms of diversity are those of space and frequency. Space diversity provides two transmission channels over a given link at the same carrier frequency, but the two paths use independent antennas that are spaced far enough apart so that the time when fading occurs over the two paths tends to be uncorrelated. Frequency diversity is used to achieve similar decorrelation properties by using two independent frequencies for transmission. Some LOS links have been found to have extreme multipath problems, and a combination of space and frequency diversity has been used (see for example [8]).

A third form of diversity that can effectively discriminate against multipath signals is angle diversity. The technique has become known as

angle diversity in general, even though there is more than one method of implementation. This report deals with a specific method, and presents the results of an initial experiment conducted to evaluate the potential of the technique in LOS microwave communication systems.

BACKGROUND OF ANGLE DIVERSITY TECHNIQUES

Angle-diversity techniques are based upon differing angles of arrival of radio signals at a receiving antenna, when the signals are a result of multipath propagation. If a multipath (delayed) signal can be effectively discriminated against by a magnitude or phase characteristic in the receiving antenna pattern, its detrimental effect can be reduced or possibly eliminated. This is the basic concept behind any form of angle diversity.

The simplest form of angle diversity has been tested by the Institute for Telecommunication Sciences (ITS), and found to be effective in certain circumstances [8], [9]. The technique used in these tests involved a single receiving antenna with its vertical pattern tilted purposely off the boresight line, such that a direct-path signal is received at a level approximately 2 to 3 dB down from maximum gain. With this orientation, a multipath signal arriving at a different angle intersects the beam pattern at a significantly lower gain. The resultant frequency selective fade is thereby reduced in comparison with the same two signals arriving at a boresight aligned antenna. Thus, a form of diversity reception is possible, whenever the off-boresight antenna can provide a better signal to the radio than the antenna aligned on the boresight. The technique is applicable to a radio system using either IF signal combining or a switched form of receiver selection.

A similar approach, but one that involves a vector combination of signals in the antenna pattern, is the subject of the tests reported here. The technical approach is briefly discussed in the following section. It is more thoroughly presented in a companion paper [10].

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The angle-diversity antenna used in the tests reported here uses a sum and difference beam approach as suggested by Signatron, Inc.* to the U.S. Army Information Systems Management Activity (ISMA) at Fort Monmouth, NJ. Under contract to ISMA, Signatron developed an angle-diversity feed designed for use in a 1.2-m (4-ft) diameter parabolic reflector. At this time in 1983, the ITS was conducting performance tests of the Digital Radio and Multiplexer Acquisition (DRAMA) system at the Pacific Missile Test Center (PMTC) at Point Mugu, CA. These tests were sponsored in part by ISMA. Consequently, the ITS was asked to conduct the angle-diversity tests in conjunction with the DRAMA tests. Comparable 1.22-m (4-ft) antennas were already in place at PMTC, as they were used in the earlier tilted antenna experiments [8]. In addition, a multichannel, tuneable, recording microwave receiver was available for use in the tests. As a result, a cooperative program was developed between ITS, Signatron, and ISMA to conduct the new angle-diversity tests at the PMTC.

TEST CONFIGURATION AND SCOPE

The test link at PMTC is a LOS path between Laguna Peak (LP) near PMTC on the California coast, and San Nicolas Island (SNI) in the Channel Islands Chain some 104.6 km (65 miles) offshore. The link is quite long, and one in which significant multipath conditions develop as a result of atmospheric inversions that set up strong refractive layers in and above the radio path. Surface reflections have been found to be very minor, primarily as a result of the patterns of the parabolic antennas and the height of the link terminals. The site at LP is approximately 426.7 m (1400 ft) above mean sea level (msl), and the SNI terminal is approximately 278 m (912 ft) above msl. The link is considered ideal for the study of multipath propagation problems.

The angle-diversity feed was received from a commercial supplier, along with a 1.22-m (4-ft) parabolic reflector. The antenna was assembled by ITS personnel at PMTC and, with assistance from PMTC, was mounted on the tower at LP early in November 1983. Signatron personnel were on site at LP on 8-9 November 1983, and participated in the initial alignment of the antenna.

The angle-diversity antenna was mounted on the southwest leg of the LP tower, at a height of approximately 11.6 m (38 ft) above ground level. This height is identical to one of two standard

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1.22-m (4-ft) parabolic antennas that was used for reference signals in the test arrangement. One of these reference antennas is mounted to the northwest leg of the LP tower, and the other is at approximately 30.5 m (100 ft) on the west face of the tower. The antenna configuration is sketched in Figure 1.

The tests were conducted in two phases. The first phase (1) was devoted to developing the fading statistics of the angle-diversity technique. Several weeks of received signal level (RSL) records were made during December 1983 and January 1984.

The transmit signal used for the tests was one of the PMTC microwave frequencies transmitted from SNI to LP at 7470 MHz. The recording receivers (designed and built by ITS) were used to record the received signal level (RSL) at the LP terminal. Table 1 lists all of the pertinent system parameters of the test link.

Table 1. System Parameters of the Angle Diversity RSL Test

(a)	Tx Freq = 7470 MHz	
(b)	Tx Power = 5 W (37 dBm)	
(c)	Antenna Gains: $G_T = 44.8$ dBi (Tx)	
	$G_R = 36.8$ dBi (Rx)	
(d)	Basic Transmission Path Loss: 150.3 dB	
(e)	Line Losses: Tx (estimated) 2.0 dB	
	Ang. Div. Δ Port 13.5 dB	
	Ang. Div. Σ Port 14.3 dB	
	Reference No. 1 19.9 dB	
	Reference No. 2 15.2 dB	

It is beyond the scope of this paper to detail the angle-diversity-feed design. Particulars may be found in the companion paper [10]. However, to make the following discussion as meaningful as possible, we shall include a fundamental description of the feed, which is basically that of a monopulse antenna.

Two independent patterns are produced by the antenna feed; one known as a sum beam (Σ port) and the other as a difference beam (Δ port). There are, therefore, two waveguide connections to the antenna, and two signals are derived at the receiving terminal. Each of these is fed to one of two independent receiver/recording channels which, in the balance of this paper, are referred to as the Σ port signal and the Δ port signal. The idealized gain patterns are shown in Figure 2 as a function of the angle of the signal arrival

with respect to an on-path orientation. Note that the Δ port pattern places a null at this point, coinciding with maximum gain for the Σ port. The objective in applying the antenna to a multipath environment is to orient the pattern in such a way that one port or the other will effectively discriminate against the multipath component as a function of the angle of arrival and the relative phase of the component with respect to the direct-path signal. The optimum orientation can only be determined from a statistical, long-term evaluation of the particular path under multipath conditions. In the first phase of the tests reported here, it was only possible to estimate the best orientation from relative short-term measurements. The antenna was first aligned on the boresight elevation, and data (RSL recordings) were taken. Based on the analyses of the fading records over several days, two operational points were established. The first was at an elevation of approximately $+0.25^\circ$, and the second at $+0.45^\circ$. These test points are shown on the beam patterns in Figure 2. It can be seen that the first point yields a gain difference on the order of 17 dB between the two angle ports, and the second point indicates a gain difference of about 10 dB. Analyses performed by Signatron, Inc. [10] have shown that the second point of operation provided the best results for the test period, and the data presented in this paper are based on that operating point. It should be noted that the off-boresight angles mentioned above are based on the idealized patterns of Figure 2, and not on the actual antenna pattern. The antenna adjustments were made on the basis of median RSL values during periods of nonfading rather than a direct measure of elevation angles.

The instrumentation used in the Phase 1 measurements is shown in the block diagram of Figure 3. The receivers were designed and built by ITS, and each channel uses a log-linear IF amplifier with a detector that provides a power level measure for the RSL. All of the signals were recorded on a 7-track analog magnetic tape machine as shown and were analyzed by Signatron, Inc. The ITS recorded these same signals in a digital data acquisition system that was used for the DRAMA performance tests. An independent analysis was performed on these data in the ITS laboratories. Examples of fading characteristics for selected intervals of time are shown in Table 2. These results are limited to an evaluation of the fade range of each signal with respect to the median levels. It can be seen that in each fading interval, this fade range is significantly lower for the angle diversity signals than that for the reference antenna. The results presented in [10] were based on more detailed analyses, in which the analyzed signals were treated on the basis of maximal ratio combining in a computer process. Thus, combined signal distributions could be compared between the space-diversity and angle-diversity signals. Results, as shown in [10], were very encouraging for the angle-diversity system.

The Phase 2 experiment was developed for actual tests of a digital radio over the PMTC

Table 2. Summary of Fading Data

Date	Test Period	Signal	Median RSL (dBm)	Total Fade Range (dB)	Max. Fade Level (dBm)	Fade Range Below Median (dB)
12/09/83	0100-0300Z 1700-1900 PST	REFERENCE	-70	53	-110	40
		Δ Port	-73	33	- 93	20
		Σ Port	-66	42	- 92	26
12/10/83	2000-2100Z 1200-1300 PST	REFERENCE	-60	47	- 95	35
		Δ Port	-67	34	- 91	24
		Σ Port	-54	36	- 83	29
12/13/83	2300-0000Z 1500-1600 PST	REFERENCE	-61	33	- 89	28
		Δ Port	-66	26	- 86	20
		Σ Port	-57	24	- 74	17
01/20/84	1000-1700Z 0200-0900 PST	REFERENCE	-62	60	-110	48
		Δ Port	-70	49	-100	30
		Σ Port	-62	52	- 95	33

link, using the angle-diversity form of reception. The test configuration used two identical DRAMA radios so that simultaneous measurements could be performed in the channel. One radio was designated as the reference system, and it was configured for space-diversity reception. The second radio was designated as the test system, and it was used to make performance measurements for the angle-diversity form of reception.

The two DRAMA radios were previously checked for equal performance when configured in the same manner. The results of a test of this nature are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Reference Tests on DRAMA Radios

Parameter	Reference Radio	Test Radio
Errored-Seconds	156	159
Total Errors	13,035,505	13,103,864
% Error Free Seconds	99.8621	99.8595
BER	8.91×10^{-6}	8.96×10^{-6}

These data were acquired over a period of four days during which the propagation was relatively stable, but with short periods of multipath. It is seen that the error performance of the two radios was nearly the same.

The original DRAMA radio tests were performed using the large, 3-m (10-ft) antennas shown in Figure 1. However, to provide comparable antenna apertures for both the space-and angle-diversity channels, these large antennas were not used for the angle-diversity tests. Instead, the 1.22-m (4-ft) antennas shown as C, D, and E in Figure 1 were used. The Signatron angle-diversity antenna was placed in location E. It was connected to the test DRAMA radio, while the two spaced antennas, C

and D, were connected to the reference DRAMA radio.

Although it is perhaps more appropriate to consider the angle-diversity technique for use in a system with predetection combining, it can also be used in a switched diversity system under certain conditions. This is the case for the DRAMA radio tests reported here. The DRAMA radio is a switched diversity radio, and at the present time the switching algorithm is based solely on the RSL. The algorithm uses a 3-dB differential switch, i.e., anytime the RSL's differ by more than 3 dB, the receiver with the highest RSL is selected as the active receiver. Therefore, in the test arrangement for the angle-diversity tests, it was imperative to balance the median RSL for the four receivers (reference and test radios). For the space-diversity (reference) radio it was only necessary to balance the line losses. The higher C antenna in Figure 1 has a larger line loss because of the additional height on the tower. For the angle-diversity (test) radio it was necessary to balance the signals both for line loss as well as the depressed median level due to the pattern gain loss in the Δ port (see Figure 2). These matters were solved through the use of low-noise preamplifiers and attenuators in the appropriate rf sections of the receivers. A block diagram of the test configuration is shown in Figure 4. Balancing adjustments were made during a period of steady signal conditions.

The data acquisition system shown in Figure 4 is centered around an LSI-11/23 CPU with dual floppy discs and a standard printer terminal. A status and alarm registry for each radio was configured, using a 16 bit parallel data board to monitor these signals sampled 10 times each second. Received signal levels were recorded digitally with this same A/D sampling rate. The spectrum of the received signals was also recorded at a response rate of one per second, sampled at a 100-Hz A/D rate. Each of the error measuring instruments was equipped with printers for on-site registry of the performance data. In addition, each instrument contained a Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter (UART) to transfer the same printer information to the computer system for recording. A digital magnetic tape deck was used to record all data. The inputs were double buffered into 5 s data blocks, and recorded in this fashion on the digital tape.

The computer system could also be used on-site to process and analyze the recorded tapes. However, most of the data were processed at a later time in the ITS laboratories on a similar data system. All of the available data have not yet been processed. Only the radio performance data have been completely analyzed, and their results are presented in the next section.

MEASUREMENTS AND RESULTS

The Phase 2 performance tests, using the angle-diversity antenna with the DRAMA radio, were begun on 17 October 1984 and continued

intermittently until 19 November 1984. The performance measure chosen for the tests was the synchronous errored-second (SES), measured by a commercial instrument. The test signal was a pseudorandom bit stream (PRBS) transmitted from SNI at the mission bit stream (MBS) rate of 12.928 Mb/s. Both MBS's of the QPR modulation scheme were transmitted using the same test code on each, but the performance measure was made on MBS-1 only. It had been determined from earlier tests on the DRAMA radios that the performance on the two MBS's was statistically the same.

The error performance data were analyzed over time blocks ranging from 1 to 6 hours in length. The total number of errored seconds in the interval were counted, and a distribution of the errors within each errored second was compiled from the process/analysis routines.

Table 4 presents a summary of the test results where the performance of the two diversity systems is listed in terms of % error free seconds (or % of error free availability). There are many other ways to make performance comparisons, but this method seems most appropriate for the particular test, and is one that conveys a total performance aspect without regard to arbitrary thresholds. We note from Table 4 that for the early part of the test period (up to 17 November) the angle-diversity system provided either better or nearly equal performance. Some periods are seen to have larger improvement than others. The last three days of the test show that the space-diversity system performed better. However, this result is discussed further below.

Table 4. Summary of Diversity Performance

Date (1984)	Hours of Multipath Fading	Performance - %	
		Error Free Seconds Space Diversity	Angle Diversity
10/18	6.8	93.452	96.667
10/19	4	90.218	91.607
10/25	12.5	80.769	86.665
10/26	10	85.605	94.445
11/15	21.6	90.378	89.262
11/16	24	96.556	97.983
11/17	7.2	81.873	73.819
11/18	21.7	95.813	95.338
11/19	10.9	94.094	89.954

The worst day for multipath fading during the test period was 16 November, where from Table 4 it is seen that the fading was observed for the entire 24-hour period. In this case the angle-diversity performance was slightly better. Two other days with comparable fading periods were the 15th and 18th of November. In these cases the performance factors are seen to be nearly the same, but favor the space-diversity system. There are a number of possible reasons for the

change in the performance factors, all of which are related to the actual multipath conditions. For example, the refractivity structure could have changed such that the median angle of arrival was significantly different from that found when the antenna was initially aligned for optimum off-path conditions. Also, the dynamics of the multipath could become significant, particularly with respect to the switched diversity radio and the switching algorithm used. In the final analysis of the initial test however, it can be concluded that the angle-diversity technique is a very suitable one. It is seen to provide either better or at least comparable performance during most of the test period. Additional analyses, where the actual multipath conditions are studied with respect to the errored-seconds or other performance measures, may be required to provide the details of the performance fluctuations.

Some added insight into the performance data can be gleaned from the distribution of the errors within the measured errored seconds. Figure 5 presents such a distribution for the data shown in Table 4. The SES instruments used in the test register the number of bit errors within each errored second. A computer routine was written to compile the error distribution in accordance with the bin-intervals as shown in Figure 5. The results show that for those errored seconds that contain fewer than 10,000 errors, the angle-diversity system displays a rather significant improvement. The two systems are very close together for those errored seconds that contained between 10,000 and 100,000 errors. However, the situation reverses rather drastically in the final error interval of >100,000. These data include those periods when the data streams were in an out-of-lock condition. The figure shows that the angle-diversity system registered more than twice the number of errored seconds in this interval than the number for the space diversity system. We do not at this time have a firm explanation for this result. It is obvious that this aspect of the data has had a disproportionate impact on the total performance summary. Had it not occurred, it can be reasoned that the angle diversity system would have performed better in all cases shown in Table 4. For example, a further examination of the errored-second data for this interval showed that the majority of contributions came from the November data. This is another reason to suspect that the multipath geometry or dynamics changed significantly between the two test periods. However, this speculation must await further analysis for verification.

One reason to speculate that the multipath dynamics could produce the result discussed above is based on a heuristic argument. Figure 2 suggests that the variation of the signal from the angle-diversity antenna could be quite rapid. This is because the operating point for the Δ port is on a very steep slope of the pattern. Small changes in angle of arrival would result in rapid signal fluctuations compared to that of the Σ port. As a result, the switched diversity radio may not have been able to keep up with the

switching rate required based on the 3-dB RSL switch differential. This factor must be investigated further, and it will be studied carefully in future tests. It should also be stated that RSL switching is perhaps not the best choice for a switched-diversity radio. It has been observed in many performance tests that there is little correlation between error performance in a digital radio and the RSL. In future tests of the DRAMA radio, a new switching algorithm using a digital signal quality monitor (SQM) will be tested. In addition, it is planned to test the DRAMA radio using a predetection combiner in place of the switched diversity configuration.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

An angle-diversity reception technique has been tested for LOS microwave digital radio. The first test phase investigated the fading characteristics of the monopulse type antenna, as reported in [10]. Only limited results of the first phase are presented here. The reader is referred to [10] for a more complete description of the antenna itself and the fading test results. A second test phase is discussed in this paper, in which the angle-diversity antenna was used with the DRAMA radio in an ongoing diversity performance program. The goal was to compare the performance of the angle-diversity system with a more conventional space-diversity configuration, both operating simultaneously in the same transmission channel. The objective was to evaluate the effectiveness of angle diversity reception in a multipath environment.

It has been concluded from these limited initial tests that this form of angle diversity has a great deal of merit for application to the LOS digital microwave communication field. This form of diversity was found to provide superior performance at times when compared to the space-diversity performance. At other times, the performance was found to be nearly the same. Only one day out of 9 days of the test period resulted in significantly poorer performance for the angle-diversity radio. The reasons for the change in performance data between the October and November test periods are discussed but are not verified.

Future tests of the angle diversity technique are being planned, in which line losses will be reduced and S/N will be improved. They will also incorporate new switching algorithms (such as SQM) for the DRAMA radio, as well as a form of predetection combining.

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Figure 1. A sketch of the receiving site tower showing the locations of the test antennas.

Figure 2. Idealized gain patterns for the angle diversity antenna.

Figure 3. Block diagram of the instrumentation and configuration of the Phase I tests.

Figure 4. Block diagram of the DRAMA radio test configuration.

Figure 5. Distribution of errors within the errored seconds recorded during the DRAMA radio tests.